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WEBQUEST TECHNOLOGY IN TEACHING SPEAKING SKILLS

Abstrak: This work highlights new technology in teaching foreign languages. Today besides acquiring foreign languages than native language, have become extremely beneficial. In the modern educational process teachers can use new technologies and forms of interaction with students and they are based on the intensification of independent activities and the direct participation of children in the educational process. Quest-technology is an innovative form of an educational organization, as it contributes to the development of the active participation of the child during the solution of search tasks.

Keywords: Internet & website resources, a computer, a foreign language, WebQuest technology, constructivism, speaking skills, motivation, conversation, communication.

In our time we must have a high level of competitiveness in achieving the goals that we set in front of ourselves. Thus, the use of technological resources, such as Internet and computers, have become necessary to achieve the full process in education. In addition, technologies are the most important strategy that increase the critical and creative thinking. Today the most popular Internet-based technology among students and teachers is Webquest. It is an entertainment game in which a player should have intellectual ability to go through many obstacles in order to achieve a goal.

The use of Internet during the learning process increases students' academic knowledge and motivates them to study. Teachers are trying to use new technologies on their lessons, such as Webquest. It is a learning style created by Professor from San Diego Burney Dodge. (University of SDGU 1995) . Web Quest is a constructive training structure that uses links to worldwide web and other important sources and it is the real task - to encourage students to explore the central open question and take part in the solution. Group process aimed at converting received information into more complex information (March 1998). Web quests are one of the roots of a constructivist approach that allows research activities, which leads to an increase in their mental abilities. Now it can play an important role in the development of English skills, and in the motivation of students in language practice and this can improve skills.

Tom is a co-author of WebQuests, rethought and expanded the definition of web quests as follows: WebQuest is a training structure that uses links in World Wide Web and other important resources. Encouraging students to study the central issue - a real task for personal development and participation in the final group process, which seeks to transform newly obtained information into a more complex understanding. The best

web quests has been done in such a way to inspire students to see thematic relations and help to contribute the real world of learning and reflect their own cognitive processes (March 2008).

Web quests are intended to ensure that students can choose the internet learning context. And Web Quest includes teamwork between groups of students to collect information and access the Internet. Web Quest for teaching languages are used by many teachers of schools and universities around the world during their lessons for several years (March 2004)

Many studies show that the Web Quest is very effective for the development of problem solving skills, a high level of thinking and creativity, an increase in motivation, critical thinking and communication with content. Torres described web quests as learning based on tasks and a lesson is prepared by teachers in the form of a web page with pre-selected links. It also requires cooperation between groups, thereby helping students to learn from each other and develop social skills and critical thinking. Besides, it impacts on improving speaking skills. There are many types of Webquest tasks on Internet, but not all of them can be suitable to a certain learners group.

Web quests contribute to integrating technologies in training and focus on how students use and find high-qualified information from the Internet. It helps students to develop independence in the performance and exchange of their ideas with each other, to discuss and solve problems (Barros & Carvalho, 2007). Using Web Quest as a pedagogical instrument is an effective and innovative way to use the Internet in learning process. Currently, students can communicate with each other and use computers as a valuable resource. (Alshumaymeri and Bamanger, 2013)

The use of web quests in education gives many advantages, helps to use time rationally, students use references to an effective search for information provided by the teacher. Another advantage of a web quest is supporting high-level of thinking. Students must read, think, analyze, synthesize and evaluate. Now the approaches that have been appeared in learning the languages improve communicative interaction and allow students to share the content of the communicative path (ELLIS, 2000). According to Torres (2007), web searches for teaching and learning languages are focused on studying the appropriate topic, which involves the use of web resources and the development of mental processes in a high level.

A speaking is defined as an interactive process of creating meaning, which includes the production, receipt and processing of information. And other scholars identified speaking as the production of hearing alarms causing various verbal reactions at the listeners. It is believed that it systematically combines the sounds for the formation of significant proposals. Another meaning of speaking is identified as a bilateral process, including true transmission of opinions, information or emotions.

In order to solve these problems can be used Webquests and to give students the opportunity to constructively learn and think critically. Webquests allow students to

play an active role in their knowledge, to rise communicative competence and increase their motivation towards the lessons. The method of constructivism includes functions like conducting complex open checks and providing students with opportunities in real, significant contexts to create their own hypotheses. In addition, the understanding of constructivism helps to create web quests.

There are factors affecting the performance of students in English. These factors play an important role in the development of students' spoken skills. Factors make students less confident in themselves, and students with higher motivation and less concern can easily and effectively speak. Thus, students should have a friendly and joint environment that can help them overcome difficulties in learning. Based on studying research literature, teachers need to understand the interests of their students, to strengthen students' confidence must choose the best learning method to keep participation in speech activities. They need to build friendly relations with their students. Teachers should expand the capabilities of their students to speak English, using some tasks that help them speak and encourage them to participate in a conversation. In addition, teachers should know when and how to correct the mistakes of students so that they are not afraid to make mistakes.

CONCLUSION

This article shows that the use of this tool not only develops communicative competence, but also increases the motivation in students, contributes to the development of critical thinking and allows differentiated training. There are some difficulties, such as the amount of time that teachers must devote to planning, the financial attachment by administrators must be done with the equipment and internet connection. So in the classrooms teachers must create positive atmosphere while teaching foreign languages.

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